

THE ESSENCE OF THE EDUCATIONAL PROCESS IN PEDAGOGY

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Abstract: We know that the primary school serves as a foundation for the future of the young generation. Didactic games are extremely important in explaining new topics to primary school students. That is why this article talks about the importance of the educational process in primary classes.

Key words: elementary school, didactic, game, education methods, types of education methods, methods of encouragement and punishment in education, activity, issue.

In modern pedagogy, there are dozens of classifications of education, some of which focus on solving practical tasks, and some of which reflect only theoretical tasks. Methods are divided into persuasion, training, encouragement and reprimand according to their specific character.

The categories of education, content, and form reveal the essence of the educational process (what it is aimed at, what it fills, what it is aimed at, and how it is completed). However, there is another important category related to the question of how to educate in the clarification of the essence of education. This is the concept of education method.

The method of education (from the Greek "methodos" - the way) is the way to achieve the goal of education. When applied to school practice, methods are methods of influencing the mind, will, feelings and behavior of students. No educator is capable of creating completely new methods of education. The problem of improving the methods is always present, each educator solves it according to his ability, enriches the general methodology based on the expression of his private views in accordance with the specific conditions of the educational process. Such private improvement of educational methods is called educational methods. Educational methods are a part of the general method, a separate movement, further definition. Figuratively speaking, methods are an unexplored path that a teacher paves the way with his students in order to achieve the set goal faster. If other educators start to use it, then gradually the methods can turn into methods with broad pillars. Knowing the methods and methods of education, mastering the ability to use them correctly is one of the important characteristics that determine the level of pedagogical skills. That is the relevance of educational methods and methods. In practice, the concept of educational tools is also distinguished.

Methods mean a unit of influence, and a tool means a set of methods.

A tool is neither a method nor a method.

For example, work is a means of education, but showing it, evaluating work, showing mistakes in work are methods. Words (in the broadest sense) are educational tools, but replicas are comparative methods. In this connection, educational methods are sometimes defined as a system of methods and tools used for the successful implementation of a set goal. Also, methods and tools will definitely be present in the structure of the method.

The purpose and content of educational methods There are no positive and negative aspects of the method, it is impossible to evaluate a certain way in the educational process as

highly effective or ineffective. The effectiveness of the method can be evaluated from the point of view of the conditions in which it is used. Appropriate selection of educational methods depends on a number of factors.

1. Goals and tasks of education. The goal not only justifies the methods, but also defines them. Whatever the goal, the methods of achieving it must be in accordance with it.

2. Content of education. Do not forget that the same task can be filled with different ideas. Therefore, it is very important to connect the methods not with the content at all, but with a clear idea.

3. Taking into account the age characteristics of the students. This or similar tasks are solved depending on the age of the students. Age is not simply a numerical indicator of how long one has lived. It reflects the acquired social experience, the level of development of psychological and moral qualities. For example, the sense of responsibility can be formed in students studying in primary education, secondary education and secondary special, vocational education institutions. However, different methods are used for the formation of this quality at each stage.

4. The level of formation of the team. In connection with the development of the collective form of self-management, the methods of pedagogical influence do not remain unchanged. As we know, the flexibility of management is a necessary condition for the successful cooperation of the educator with the students.

5. Individual characteristics of students. General methods, general programs cannot be the basis of educational interaction. It is necessary to adjust them individually and personally. A humanistic pedagogue tries to use methods that allow each person to develop his or her individuality, to preserve his or her individuality, to realize his or her "I".

6. Educational conditions. It includes material, psychophysiological, and sanitary-hygienic relations in the classroom: the climate in the team, the method of pedagogical leadership, etc. It is known that there are no abstract conditions, they are always concrete. Their combination is visible in certain cases. Pedagogical situations are the conditions in which education takes place.

7. Educational tools. Educational methods are formed from educational tools that appear as components of the educational process. There are other educational tools that are closely related to the methods and are used together. For example, visual aids, visual arts and music, mass media that provide necessary support for the effective application of methods.

8. The level of acquiring pedagogical skills. The teacher usually chooses only the methods that he knows and knows how to use. Many methods are complex and require a lot of effort on the part of the teacher. Educators who avoid such responsibility try to organize activities without them. As a result, it is less effective than using methods based on different images, different goals, tasks, and conditions.

9. Time of education. When time is short and the goal is big, "strongly moving" methods are used, and in favorable conditions, "sparing" methods of education are used. It is necessary to divide education into "strongly motivating" and "sympathetic" methods: the first is connected with reprimanding and coercion, and the second is connected with exhortation and constant training.

10. Expected result. When choosing a method, the educator must be confident that he will succeed. For this, it is necessary to know in advance what the method used will lead to.

In this case, the general characteristic of the method reflects its orientation, originality, applicability. The general methods of education, which are distinguished by the more generalization of the methods, are firmly connected to this classification. It includes methods of persuasion, organization of activities, motivation of students' behavior. I.S. In Marenko's classification, groups of educational methods are named as follows: explanatory-reproductive, problem-based, teaching and training methods, motivational, inhibitory, management, self-education. ra methods can be divided into two groups:

1. Ethical standards that influence the formation of motives, the formation of imagination, understanding, and ideas.
2. Affecting the formation of habits that determine one or another type of behavior.

Methods depend on the purpose and content of education. The methods of education are aimed at forming the qualities of a well-rounded person. Therefore, taking into account the level of development of students is an important condition for the effective use of educational methods. Students react differently to this or that educational effect. It depends on their special characteristics, the level of upbringing, the extent to which educational methods are chosen appropriately and effectively, and how skillfully they are used.

The correct choice of educational methods helps to increase the activity of self-education of students in solving educational tasks positively. For example, in the process of working with first-grade students, the teacher uses the method of explaining to them the rules of behavior of students, the importance of having a clear agenda, and the need for students to follow a strict order when teaching students new work activities. In addition to explaining, he trains them to enter the classroom correctly, to greet the teacher and students, and to maintain discipline. At the same time, the students of the first grade are used to the above processes during the lesson. In this process, the positive work they have done, the results of their educational work, require encouragement. It can be seen that the teacher uses different methods and methods when conducting the educational process with students. The variety of educational methods shows the need to divide and classify them into types. Therefore, they can be divided into groups, taking into account their special characteristics. Every teacher (educator) who wants to achieve educational results should thoroughly master educational methods and their essence.

The task of the first group of methods is to create an understanding and knowledge about the rules and norms of life, ethics, labor relations in the social mind of the student. In the process of education, these rules and norms become the beliefs, confidence and life views of a person. This group includes spiritual, moral, aesthetic, ideological, legal, physical, ecological, economic, etc. it is possible to include conversations on the content and the methods of showing examples. Using the methods of the second group, the student forms habits related to the spiritual content. The behavior of the student is formed in accordance with the content of social education on the basis of moral habits and on the ground of activity. Activity is an important resource that enriches the experience of social relations and social behavior of students.

Among the methods of the second group, the method of pedagogical demand is important. Pedagogical demand can be the fulfillment of various tasks, i.e. expressing the norms of social behavior, performing a specific task that needs to be performed by participating in this or that activity, and encouraging one or another action.

Claims can be made directly or indirectly. Direct requirements are in the form of a strict command or instruction, a task, a guiding description. Indirect demands are expressed in the form of advice, request, rebuke, interest in activities, with the aim of arousing a sense of

experience and aspiration. Requirements imply that the student has some level of awareness, reason, purpose, and belief. At the same time, the teacher must pay special attention to the standards of the requirements imposed on the students. In the process of useful activities and specially organized tasks, positive behavior and characters are taught. Teaching is an encouraging activity to organize various actions and practical activities organized by students in a planned and systematic way in order to transform social behavior into a normal form. Teaching is considered an effective tool at all stages of education and development of students. Exercises in the activity are aimed at training the habits of work, social activity, team activity and interaction. Training is closely related to teaching. If the basis of teaching lies in the child's mastery of the activity process, then the activity of training is of special importance for the individual. Training relies heavily on learning to control repetition, reinforcement, and improvement, which increasingly become the basis of social behavior.

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